

STUDIES ON THE TURBIDITY OF COLLOIDAL SUSPENSIONS OF LAYER LATTICE MINERALS

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The changes in turbidity of aqueous suspensions of bentonite, kaolinite and muscovite mica have been followed with progressive dilution, and the relative intensities of scattered light, which is the reciprocal of turbidity, are plotted against concentration. All the curves show well defined maxima and the concentrations of the colloidal salts corresponding to the maxima depend on the nature of the exchangeable cations. The minerals studied show characteristic differences as regards the above two.

According to Ostwald ("Licht und Farbe in Kolloiden", Dresden, 1924) turbidity of a suspension may be defined as the reciprocal of the intensity of light scattered by the particles in suspension. The theory of the scattering of light has been developed from various points of view. Rayleigh (*Phil. Mag.*, 1899, **47**, 375) studied the diffraction of extremely small particles as a function of size.

The case of spherical metallic particles of large diameters was developed by Mie (*Ann. Physik*, 1908, **25**, 377) and also by Debye (*ibid.*, 1909, **30**, 57). Gans (*ibid.*, 1912, **37**, 88 ; 1915, **47**, 270) investigated the influence of deviations from spherical shape. Rayleigh's theory is shown to be a special case of Mie's when the size of the particle is less than the wave-length of the incident light. As the particles become coarser in size, the intensity of scattered light increases till the size reaches the order of the wave-length of the light, after which the intensity decreases, preceded by a maximum. Mie's theory has been experimentally verified by a number of investigators (Bechold and Heber, *Kolloid Z.*, 1922, **31**, 8 ; Gribnaum, *ibid.*, 1936, **77**, 289 ; 1938, **82**, 15 ; Casperson, *ibid.*, 1932, **60**, 151) using colloidal solutions.

In the experiments done for the verification of Mie's theory in the case of colloidal suspensions mostly hydrophobic sols were used. Colloidal particles of clay minerals have a layer lattice structure, and hence non-spherical in shape. Moreover, they are more or less hydrated and get dispersed in water, the extent of dispersion depending on the nature of the minerals as well as on the exchangeable cation saturating it. Thus, the well known high dispersity of alkali-saturated clays is taken advantage of in determining the clay content of soils. The amount of dispersion will naturally depend on the ratio of colloid to water, which is the usual dispersion medium. When therefore a colloidal clay is diluted with water, the original particles will no doubt be reduced in number, but they will produce by dispersion or disaggregation particles of smaller sizes, which will increase in number and become still finer as dilution proceeds, until a limiting size, if any, is reached. In view of these two non-exclusive effects it becomes interesting to follow the changes in turbidity of aqueous colloidal suspensions of these minerals with progressive dilution.

EXPERIMENTAL

The clay fractions obtained from the following samples of minerals were used for the present investigation.

1. Bentonite, containing the only clay mineral montmorillonite.
2. Muscovite mica.
3. Kaolinite.

The clay fractions from the powdered bentonite and kaolinite were obtained according to the International Soda method (Wright, "Soil Analysis", 1939). Sheets of mica were cut into very small pieces and then wet-ground in an electrically driven agate mortar and pestle. The clay fraction was afterwards separated by sedimentation. They were then converted into the hydrogen systems by continuous leaching with dilute hydrochloric acid, washed with distilled water and finally suspended in conductivity water. Portions of the hydrogen systems were converted into

the colloidal salts of Na, K, Ca and Ba (Mukherjee, *Indian Soil Sci. Bull.*, 1942, No. 4, p. 188) by adding to them the corresponding alkalis in amounts equivalent to the base exchange capacity of the clays as measured by the method of Parker (*J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1929, 21, 1030). The mixtures of the clay and alkalis were kept for about a month to attain equilibrium. The colloid contents of the suspensions were calculated in terms of the hydrogen systems. The relative turbidity of the suspensions as obtained directly from the drum-head reading of the Zeiss Trubungsmesser, is the reciprocal of the relative intensity of scattered light recorded in the diagrams below.

The colloidal salts taken from the stock solutions were diluted with known quantities of conductivity water in steam-cleaned Jena bottles and allowed to attain hydration equilibrium. The turbidities observed from day to day varied until after about a week constant values were obtained.

TABLE I

Conc. (g. per litre.)	Turbidity.	Reciprocal of turbidity (i.e. intensity).	Intensity for 1 g. per litre.	Intensity × conc.
Potassium bentonite sol.				
0.218	42.0	0.0240	0.110	—
0.254	38.0	0.0263	0.103	—
0.305	29.0	0.0345	0.113	—
0.380	25.0	0.0400	0.105	—
0.610	15.0	0.0666	0.109	—
1.220	10.0	0.1000	0.082	—
1.830	9.0	0.1110	0.0607	0.203
2.440	11.0	0.0900	0.037	0.219
3.050	13.0	0.0770	0.025	0.234
3.660	13.0	0.0555	0.015	0.201
4.270	21.0	0.0480	0.011	0.204
4.880	27.0	0.0370	0.0075	0.181
5.490	29.5	0.0340	0.0061	0.186
Potassium kaolinite sol.				
0.2127	14.0	0.0714	0.3355	—
0.2360	13.0	0.0769	0.3258	—
0.266	12.5	0.0800	0.3007	—
0.304	12.0	0.0833	0.2740	—
0.3545	11.5	0.0870	0.2454	—
0.4254	11.0	0.0909	0.2136	0.039
0.5317	13.5	0.0740	0.1390	0.039
0.709	15.5	0.0645	0.0909	0.045
0.85	19.5	0.0512	0.0602	0.043
1.7	48.0	0.0208	0.0122	0.036
2.55	82.0	0.0122	0.0047	0.031
3.40	166.5	0.0060	—	—
Potassium mica sol.				
0.027	83.0	0.012	0.444	—
0.055	47.0	0.021	0.381	—
0.110	23.5	0.0425	0.366	—
0.221	13.5	0.074	0.334	—
0.442	10.5	0.095	0.214	0.042
0.885	15.0	0.066	0.074	0.058
1.77	25.0	0.040	0.022	0.071
3.54	52.0	0.019	0.005	0.071

N.B.—Similar results have been observed in other bentonites, micas and kaolinites but are omitted for want of space.

TABLE II

System.	Colloid content corresponding to maximum intensity in g perlitre.	Value of maximum intensity per g. of colloid.
Sodium bentonite	3.05	0.0280
Hydrogen bentonite	1.008	0.135
Potassium bentonite	1.830	0.0607
Barium bentonite	1.220	0.091
Potassium kaolinite	0.4254	0.2136
Barium kaolinite	0.3545	0.2560
Calcium kaolinite	0.3545	0.2967
Sodium mica	0.442	0.25
Potassium mica	0.442	0.214

DISCUSSION

The variations of the relative intensity of scattered light of the different colloidal salts with concentration are graphically shown in Figs. 1-3. The following points of interest emerge from them.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

All the curves show well defined maxima ; the concentrations of the colloidal salts corresponding to the maxima depend on the nature of the exchangeable cations ; and the minerals studied show characteristic differences as regards the above two.

The sizes of the colloidal particles vary within a wide range. The size distribution is not known, but the largest particles are of the order of 10^{-4} cm. and the smaller, of the order of 10^{-6} cm. Moreover, the particles are non-spherical in shape. Rayleigh's theory is therefore applicable to these systems only in a restricted sense.

The curves showing the maxima are similar to the intensity of scattered light size variations as demanded by the theory. A progressive change in particle size with dilution is thus indicated. This appears to fit in with the following picture of the state of affairs. In the most concentrated sols studied the minerals happen to be considerably aggregated, the particle size of the aggregates being large enough to obey Mie's theory. Dilution decreases the number of aggregates, as well as breaks them into those of smaller sizes which are still large enough to obey Mie's theory. Towards the initial stages, *i.e.* the low dilution range, the latter effect appears to be prominent. The right hand part of the curve, which is hyperbolic in nature, depicts this condition. The

constancy of the product of the relative intensity and colloid concentration (cf. Table I, column 5) corroborates the same. At higher dilutions disaggregation takes place to a greater extent and the effect of particle size becomes more and more predominant. The particles having the critical sizes necessary for Rayleigh's law to hold good gradually increase in number so that the intensity of scattered light begins under the circumstances to decrease. The two opposing effects give rise to a maximum after which disaggregation no longer takes place, *i.e.*, at this concentration of the colloid corresponding to the maximum it disperses into the ultimate size. Further dilution therefore causes a decrease in the number of these smallest particles. Since the effect of particle size is more predominant, the decrease in the intensity (I) of scattered light after the maximum is very sharp. The fact that the value of I in the range of high dilutions after the maximum is almost constant (vide Table I, column 4), when expressed per unit weight of the colloid, suggests that dilution in this region causes only a proportionate decrease in the total number of scattering centres, *i.e.*, particles. This can only happen if disaggregation is complete at or about the maximum.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

It will be seen from Figs. 4 and 5, in which the colloids saturated with the same kind of cations have been compared, that the maximum values of I *i.e.*, the minimum turbidities occur at a higher concentrations of the montmorillonite than either the micas or kaolinites. This shows that the breaking up of the aggregates is complete at a higher concentration of the former than the latter. The mica and the kaolinite seem to show the maxima almost at the same concentration. This is expected if one takes into consideration the crystalline structures of these minerals. Montmorillonite is known to have a very open structure and to swell markedly in water. It is therefore highly unstable in its interaction with water. Mica and kaolinite have, on the other hand, compact structures and interact slowly with water so that disaggregation goes on up to very high dilutions.

The concentrations at which the minimum values of turbidity occur, as well as values of the latter, depend markedly on the nature of the saturating cation. In this connection the figures given in Table II are illustrative. The colloid content corresponding to almost the same order of the turbidity are much greater in the case of montmorillonites than in the micas and kaolinites (*vide supra*). The values of the maximum intensity expressed on the basis of 1 g. of the colloidal salts (column 3, Table II), when considered for a particular mineral, show a definite lyotrope effect of the saturating cations. For instance, the orders are: $H > Ba > K > Na$ in montmorillonites; $Ca > Ba > K$ in kaolinites; and $Na > K$ in micas. K is a constituent of the mica lattice and causes a greater dispersion and a higher turbidity of K-mica compared to Na-mica suspensions.

FIG. 5

A comparison of the curves in Figs. 4 and 5 further shows that at the same concentration of the colloids, montmorillonites have much higher values of turbidity than the micas and the kaolinites. This once again points to the much more compact structure of the micas and kaolinites and the highly dispersed nature of the montmorillonites.

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